

Study of Basaltic Soils Along the Toposequence of Aya River in Ogoja, Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

An investigation was carried out on selected properties of basaltic soils along the toposequence of Aya river in Ogoja Cross river state. The soils are deep and occur on a gentle and undulating landscape with a gradient of <4%. Three profile pits were dug in each of the mapping units identified as crest, mid-slope and valley bottom. Each Pedon had four distinct genetic horizons (Ap, AB, Bt1 and Bt2). The dominant matrix for the Ap horizon was dark brown (7.5YR3/4), brown (7.5YR6/4) and yellowish brown (10YR6/8) for pedons I, II and III respectively. The particle size distribution data indicates the preponderance of sand fraction while the percentage sand mean values are 82.45 %, 81.45 % , 85.78 % and 81.0 % for pedons III, II and I respectively. The soils reaction pH_{H2O} is assessed as strongly acidic ranging from 5.25-5.75. The exchangeable Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺ and K⁺ are in low concentrations but are within the threshold of critical limits. Organic carbon and total nitrogen and available P were generally low (N: 1.7-1.1 g/kg; OC:7.3-5.1 g/kg and P:18.25- 12.60 g/kg). The Organic C/N ranged from 3 – 7 and Ca/Mg had mean of 1.40, 1.36 and 1.31 in pedons I, II, and III respectively. The base saturation (%BS) was high to very high (64.70-79.26 %) while effective cation exchange capacity was generally low (2.03 cmol/kg, 2.29 cmol/kg, and 1.93 cmol/kg for pedons I, II, and III respectively). The soil on the toposequence of Aya river showed evidence of oxic properties with absence of weatherable minerals in the sub stratum. The soil suitability class were moderately suitable with limitations in pH and low soil organic matter content. The soils were classified as Isohyperthermic ustalfs which corresponded to Arenic Luvisols (pedons 1 and 2) with fluvic characteristics in pedon 3 (WRB, 2006). Soil quality of the studied soils is low due to the established unfavourable fertility indicators; hence soil conservation and use of integrated soil fertility management- organic sources (compost manure), inorganic sources (NPK fertilizers) and crop rotation as well as conservational tillage is recommended.

Keywords: basaltic materials, toposequence, morphology, classification, suitability

Introduction

Soils formed on basaltic parent materials are usually rich in ferromagnesian minerals mainly plagioclase feldspar (which are rich in Ca and/or Na- $\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_4$ or $\text{NaAl}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8$) and pyroxene [$(\text{Mg, Fe})_2\text{SiO}_4$] (Esu et al., 2015) and (Ojo-Atere et al., 2011). Esu et al., (2015) in their investigation in the morphological, physicochemical and mineralogical properties of soils developed from basalt at not too far away Ikom, they established that 77.7% of the mineralogy is composed of kaonilite, 10.75% is Fe bearing minerals (goethite and hematite) and they concluded that these soils are dominated by highly resistant minerals, a sign of soil in an oxic state of weathering where leaching, eluviation-illuviation, laterization and faunal pedoturbation are common features (Esu et al., 2015 and Eshett, 1987). In many tropical soils, where excessive rainfall and leaching of the bases results in the acidification of the soils through Fe- Al saturation in the exchange site while Nsor and Akamigbo (2015), also observed the problem of plinthization in the soils of central cross river state.

Topography depends on the configuration of the system in the of elevation, slope and landscape expositions. Differences in topography can cause wide variations in soils within the confines of a single field. Topography determines the local distribution or disposal of the precipitation and determines the extent to which water tables influence soil genesis (Foth, 1990). Topography hastens or delays the work of climatic factors in pedogenesis with respect to soil horizon development (Brady and Weil, 1999). Toposequence is used interchangeably with catena by many soil scientists, and catena concepts have emanated as slope- soil evolutionary process (Esu et al., 2008). The soils differ as a result of erosion, transportation and deposition of surficial materials as well as leaching, translocation and deposition of chemical and particulate constituents in the soil. These processes result in morphological changes associated with soil colour and horizonation as a result of hydrology related to topographic position (Juo and Moorman, 1980). Soil colour is one of the important basic properties which help in identifying the kinds of soils and recognize the successions of soil horizons or layer in the soil profile and it gives the physical structure of the soil some intrinsic imprint that are related to topography. It has been used for soil identification and qualitative measurements of soil properties and serves as a useful tool in field studies (Noshadi et al., 2013). While Wakene (2003), stated soil colour is function of pH, redox reaction, and organic matter. A change in soil colour from adjacent soil also indicates a difference in the soil mineral origin or soil development, geologic origin and degree of weathering of the soil material and leaching or accumulation of chemical compounds such as iron, which may greatly influence soil quality (Fisher and Binkley, 2000). Though not all soils are strongly correlated with terrain attributed, much less can be linked to them in a straightforward functional way (Sobieraj et al., 2002), this is even more complex within agricultural field where different types of land use types are practiced. Landscape position influences rainfall, drainage and erosion, water velocity on a slope affects deposition of materials in suspension, the largest sized particles like sand are the first to drop out of suspension, fine clay size particles can be carried further away from the base of the slope before they are deposited. Hill slope orientation also affects the microclimate of a place, inclined surface facing into the sun tend to be warmer and drier than flatter surface facing away from the sun (Atofarati et al, 2012). Soils developed on a toposequence have been found to be suitable in the production of crops such as tree crop (*Theobroma cacao* and

Gmelina aborarea), food crops (yam, cassava and maize) and vegetables (tomato, fluted pumpkin and garden egg etc). These were reported by Eshett (1987) for basaltic soils on the toposequence at Ikom in Northern Cross river state, Nigeria. Soil in the tropics are extremely diverse, they ranged from young fertile to senile soils. The objectives of this study were to characterise and classify the basaltic soil along the toposequence of Aya river in Ogoja Cross River state and study its suitability classification for selected crops.

Materials and Methods

Site Description

The study area was along the toposequence of Aya River in Ogoja Local Government Area of Cross River State. It lies between latitude 6°41.38'N and longitude 8°58.03'E. The area has distinct rainy (March to October) and dry seasons. The mean annual rainfall in the study area ranges from 1728 - 2200 mm with double maxima in the months of July and September. Mean annual temperature varies from 22.4° to 32.5°C while the mean annual relative humidity varied from 74 to 79%. The climate of the area is sub-humid tropical, and its vegetation is forest-grassland-savanna. The soils are generally derived from the basaltic and alluvium of either false-bedded sandstone or the upper coal measure (Asadu, 1990) with gentle undulating plains with scattered rock outcrops. The hydrology is governed by Aya River (it raises from Obudu plateau) which is a major tributary of Cross River. The soils are well drained with few poorly drained soils (loamy sand to sandy clay) which are used for paddy rice and sugarcane cultivation. Its vegetation is characterized as forest- grassland-savannah (transitional vegetation type). Agriculture is the major socioeconomic activities in the area with cottage industries in fishing and agricultural related enterprises. The major farm produce is yam (*Dioscorea* spp), plantain (*Musa paradisiaca*), cassava (*Manihot esculenta*), rice (*Oryza sativa*), ground nut, maize, soybean, bambara nut (*Vigna subterranean*) and vegetables (water leaf and fluted pumpkin- *Telifairia occidentalis*). The area is rich in forest resources but with the rate of current deforestation amidst uncontrolled access. Oil palm (*Elaeis guineensis*) and cocoa (*Theobroma cacao*) are common but value addition to oil palm fruits is also a major cottage industry alongside cassava processing.

Field Work

Three mapping units were identified and classified based on physiographic position along the toposequence and associated landuse. A stratified random sampling technique was adopted in the study. The profile pits were dug at upper, mid-slope and lower part of the slope. A total of three profile pits was sunk and described following the guidelines of FAO, (2006). Soil samples were taken for routine physical and chemical analysis.

Laboratory Analysis

The pH was determined by glass electrode pH meter both in 1:2.5 soil/ liquid suspension of water and KCl (Henderson et al., 1993). Particle size analysis was by hydrometer method (Gee and Or, 2002). Organic carbon was determined by wet dichromate method by Udo et al., (2009). Total nitrogen was determined by micro-Kjeldahl digestion method as modified by Udo et al., (2009). Extraction of available phosphorus was done using Bray 1 method. Exchangeable cations (K^+ , Ca , Mg^{2+} , and Na^+) were extracted by neutral

normal ammonium acetate, K^+ and Na^+ in the extraction were determined by flame photometer (Udo et al., 2009) while Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} were by atomic absorption spectrophotometer. Cation exchange capacity was by summation method. Exchangeable acidity was determined in 1NKCl extracting solution with 0.5N NaOH using phenolphthalein indicator by titration method of Mclean as described by Udo et al., (2009). Bulk density was measured by core method (Grossman and Reinsch, 2002). Total porosity (P_o) was obtained from bulk density (ℓ_p) values with assumed particle density (ℓ_s) 2.65 g cm^{-3} as follows, Porosity (P_o) = $100 - (\ell_p/\ell_s) \times 100/1$

Statistical analysis was performed using Genstat statistical package for the analysis of variance and treatment mean compared using least significant difference at 5% level of probability.

Table 1. Location Coordinates and Elevation

Position	Profile code	Elevation (M.A.S.L)	North-East coordinates
Lower	III	110	$6^{\circ}39'27.9''N$, $8^{\circ}59'23.0''E$
Mid-slope	II	108	$6^{\circ}39'27.3''N$, $8^{\circ}59'21.8''E$
Upper (Crest)	I	119	$6^{\circ}39'27.3''N$, $8^{\circ}59'20.4''E$

Results and Discussion

Morphological properties of the studied soils are shown in table 2, the physiographic mapping units have different colour matrix range, and all the horizons are deep and well drained characterized by loose top soil. The peds are generally arranged in weak to moderate granular and sub angular blocky, clear wavy horizon boundaries and soils have fine and medium roots and pronounced faunal activities in the epipedons. The soil at the slope appears to be shallow with a depth of 92 cm while the depth at both the midslope and valley bottom are well above 110 cm, this was in agreement with the findings of Ofem and Esu (2015). The soil colour varies from the crest to the valley bottom, the crest is dominated by brownish yellow (10YR6/8) at 0-25 cm and strong brown (7.5YR5/8) at depth of 25-47cm, reddish yellow (7.5YR5/8) at 47-76 cm and 5YR7/8 at 76-92 cm. The mid-slope is dominated by brownish colour 7.5YR4/4 at 0-17cm, dark yellowish brown (10YR4/6) at 17-39cm, yellowish red (5YR6/6) at 39-100cm. the soils at the valley bottom had dark brown (7.5YR3/4) at 0-20cm, strong brown (7.5YR5/8) at the sub surface profiles, the variation in colour matrix of the soils is a reflection of the sequence of drainage condition and physiographic positions and this conformed with the works of Nuga et al., (2006) and Akamigbo and Asadu (1986). The presence of many fine pores, many fine roots and fauna activities in Ap horizon of the pedons are indicative of the desirable effect of soil organic matter which enhances aggregate stability (Daniel, et al., 2000). Termites and earthworms were observed as agents of micro-faunaturbation in the study areas.

Table 2. Morphological Properties of Soils Along the Toposequence of Aya River

Depth (cm)	Horizon	Colour	Text Ure	Structure	Horizon bound	Consist.	Veg.	Root presence
Crest Pedon 1								
0-25	Ap	Yellowish brown (10YR6/8)	LS	Gr	SC	NSNP		Many(vf-f)
25-47	AB	Strong brown (7.5YR5/8)	LS	Gr	SC	NSNP		Common(vf-f)
47-76	Bt1	Reddish yellow (7.5YR6/6)	SL	Gr	SC	NSNP	SR	Few(f)
76-92	Bt2	Reddish yellow (5YR7/8)	SL	Gr	SC	FRSST		Very few(F)
Midslope Pedon 2								
0-17	Ap	Brown (7.5YR6/4)	LS	Gr	CW	Crumbly		Many(vf-f)
17-39	AB	Dark yellowish brown(10YR6/4)	LS	SAB	CW	Friable		Common(vf-f)
39-74	BT1	Yellowish Red (5YR6/6)	SCL	SAB	CW	Extremely firm	SR	Few(f)
74-135	BT2	Yellowish (5YR7/8)	Red SCL	SAB	CW	Extremely firm		Very few(F)
Valley Pedon3								
0-20	Ap	Dark brown (7.5YR3/4)	LS	Gr	CS	Friable		Many(vf-f)
20-44	AB	Strong brown (7.5YR5/8)	LS	Gr	CS	Friable	SR	common(vf-c)
44-72	Bt1	Strong brown (7.5YR4/6)	S	Gr	CS	Firm and sticky		Few(f)
72-110	Bt2	Strong brown (7.5YR5/6)	SL	Gr	CS	Very firm and sticky		Very Few(f)

Colour: YR = reddish yellow, Structure: Gr= granular, SAB = subangular blocky, Consistence: NSNP= non sticky non plastic. FRSST = friable slighty sticky, Roots: C= coarse, vf = very fine, vf = very few, f= few, f=fine, vegetation: SR= secondary regrowth

The physical properties of the studied soils are shown in table 3. The particle size distribution data indicates the preponderance of sand in all the pedons in the study area; this suggests they have quartzite in its geology. The mean values of sand are 82.45 % (pedon III), 81.45 % (pedon II), 85.78 % and 81.0 % (pedon I). This is in contrast with the several authors who reported the dominance of clay in the textural class. The difference in the textural class may be due to intense and prolonged precipitations in the study area.

The silt content showed no regular pattern in pedons I and III but without a fluctuation the profile in pedon II. Clay content was generally higher than silt content in all of the studied pedons. The highest clay content was established in pedon II (17.15%). This trend is a common physical feature with soils in this zone and this is due to weathering of silt fraction into clay. The silt clay ratio (SCR) in the studied profile showed mean values of <1, which indicates of reserve of weatherable minerals in the substratum as typical of kandiuustalfts (USDA, 2015). The SCR is an index for gauging extent of weathering in soils (Oleghe and Chokor, 2015).

The textural classes range from loamy sand in the top soil (Ap horizon) and sandy loam in the subsoil. Pedon II has loamy sand in (Ap horizon) and sandy clay loam (subsoil), pedon III had loamy sand (Ap horizon) and sandy loam (subsoil). The mean values of bulk density were 1.24 g/cm^{-3} , 1.17 g/cm^{-3} , 1.27 g/cm^{-3} for pedons I, II and III respectively. The bulk density decreased with profile depth though values obtained are within the range for good rooting crops (Soil Survey Staff, 2006 and Ladon, 1991).

The porosity values range from 52 % - 56 %. These porosity values indicate good soil-air conditions. This meets with the study of Chude et al., (2011); which noted that soil physical properties are dominant factors affecting the usage of soils. This is because the success or failure of agricultural venture (crop wise) is often hinges on the physical properties of the soil and physical properties are more difficult to change than chemical properties (Okolo et al., 2015). Several authors (Sanchez, 2019) pointed out that the soil texture is less susceptible to change

Table 3. Physical Properties of Soils Along the Toposequence of Aya River

Horizon	Depth (cm)	Sand (%)	Clay (%)	Silt (%)	SCR	TC	BD g/cm ³	Po	MC %
Crest (pedon I)									
Ap	0-22	86.2	11.4	2.4	0.21	LS	1.27	52	8.31
AB	25-47	85.2	13.4	1.4	0.1	LS	1.42	46	8.48
Bt1	47- 76	82.2	14.4	3.4	0.24	SL	1.33	50	9.44
Bt2g	76- 92	76.2	18.4	5.4	0.24	SL	1.05	60	14.9
Mean		82.45	14.4	3.15	0.21		1.27	52	10.28
SD±		4.5	2.94	1.71	0.08		0.08	3.12	3.123
CV		5.46	20.42	54.29	38.1		12.6	30.35	30.35
Midslope (pedon II)									
Ap	0-17	89.2	9.4	1.4	0.15	LS	1.19	55	8.03
AB	17-39	85.2	13.4	1.4	0.1	LS	1.29	51	6.32
Bt1	39-74	78.2	20.4	1.4	0.07	SL	1.11	58	9.16
Bt2g	74-135	73.2	25.4	1.4	0.06	SCL	1.07	60	11.7
Mean		81.45	17.15	1.4	0		1.17	56	8.8
SD±		7.14	7.14	0	0.1		0.1	2.26	2.26
CV		8.77	41.63	0	4.45-7.55		48.55	25.68	25.68
Valley bottom (pedon III)									
Ap	0-20	86.8	7.3	5.9	0.81	LS	1.28	52	8.9
AB	20-44	89.8	8.3	1.9	0.23	LS	1.16	56	20.1
Bt1	44- 72	91.8	7.9	0.3	0.04	S	1.25	53	6.62
Bt2g	72-110	74.7	13.1	12.2	0.93	SL	1.28	52	5.92
Mean		85.78	9.15	5.06	0.5		1.24	53	10.39
SD±		7.66	2.67	5.3	0.43		0.06	6.6	6.6
CV		8.93	29.18	104.74	86		4.84	63.52	63.52
LSD(5%)		10.92	30.2	39.16	16.5		0.01	17.6	59

SCR= silt/ clay ratio, TC= textural class, BD g/cm³, Po= total porosity, MC = moisture content

The chemical properties of the studied soil are as presented in table 4. The pH had mean values of 5.50, 5.46 and 5.64 for pedons I, II and III respectively, the soil reaction generally ranges from strongly acidic in the topsoil to moderately acidic in the subsoil (acidity decreased with profile depth). The acidity may be due to leaching caused by precipitations and urea fertilizer application (many of the farmers are found to apply urea fertilizers in crop production). This indicates that the soils are strongly acidic and shows that there are significant exchangeable Al^{3+} and H^+ hence the entire soil will have net negative charges on soil colloids and this will engender cation adsorption on the soil exchange complex (Kolay, 2002).

According to Osodeke, (2017) such acidic cause fixing of nutrients such as phosphorous, potassium, and sulphur hence making them unavailable for plant uptake. The exchangeable Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and K^+ are in low concentrations but are within the threshold of critical limits for deficiencies and likely in response to fertilization (Adisa et al., 2016 and Haby et al., 1990). The mean value for exchangeable Ca^{2+} was 0.86 cmol/kg, 0.78cmol/kg and 0.82 cmol/kg in pedons I, II and III respectively. The concentration of exch. Mg^{2+} is close to that of exch. Ca^{2+} with mean values of 0.61 cmol/kg, 0.57 cmol/kg and 0.63 cmol/kg in pedons I, II and III respectively. Exchangeable Mg^{2+} below 0.28 cmol/kg would manifest as deficiency in maize (FMANR, 1990).

Organic carbon and total nitrogen and available P were generally rated low to moderate (N: 1.7-1.1 g/kg; OC: 7.3-5.1 g/kg and P: 18.25- 12.60 g/kg). The obtained value of TN, OC and available P obtained were higher than those reported by Ofem and Esu (2015). These variations may be due to climatic factors and agronomy practices.

The soil would require higher amount of N and P fertilizers to maintain their adequate supply. The application of gypsum is required to increase the soil pH, release the fixed phosphorous and boost Ca and Mg in the soil (Osodeke, 2017, Esu et al., 2015). The mean values of exch. K^+ were assessed as very low 0.01 cmol/kg in all of the studied pedons. This is very critical for crop development as K^+ is macro element in plant nutrition. Therefore, K^+ in the profile is inadequate for crop utilization (Imadojemu et al, 2017). The org. C/N ratio and Ca/Mg ratio were range from very low to low.

The org. C/N is important for determining mineralization and immobilization of nitrogen, the C/N ranged from 3.15 – 6.64 which is below 25 favours mineralization set by Paul and Clark (1989). The established Ca/Mg ratio of <5.1 indicates low activity clay (Brady and Weil, 2014). The Ca/Mg ratio had mean values of 1.40, 1.36 and 1.31 in pedons I, II, and III respectively. The percentage base saturation (%BS) was high to very high (64.70-79.26 %), a similar result was reported by Ofem and Esu (2015).

The effective cation exchange capacity was assessed as low, the highest mean value was obtained in pedon II (2.29 cmol/kg). This means that the soil requires integrated soil fertility management (organic composting), inorganic (N.P.K fertilizers) and conservation agriculture (crop rotation, sub soil tilling etc).

Table 4. Chemical Properties of Soils along the Toposequence of Aya River

Horizon	Depth (cm)	pH H ₂ O ^(1:2.5)	% Org. Carbon	%TN	C/N	Av. P (ppmP/g)	TEA	Ca	Mg	Na	K	TEB	ECEC	%BS	Ca/Mg
						cmol/kg		cmol/kg		cmol/kg		cmol/kg			
Valley Bottom (pedon III)															
Ap	0-20	5.35	0.79	0.15	5.27	14.07	0.4	0.84	0.6	0.05	0.01	1.48	1.88	79	1.4
AB	20-44	5.55	0.48	0.15	3.2	14.42	0.4	0.84	0.6	0.05	0.01	1.48	1.88	79	1.4
Bt1	44-72	5.65	0.39	0.18	2.17	25	0.2	0.88	0.62	0.05	0.01	1.56	1.76	86	1.42
Bt2g	72-110	5.45	0.39	0.2	1.95	12	1	0.88	0.63	0.05	0.02	1.6	2.6	62	1.4
Mean		5.5	0.51	0.17	3.15	16.36	0.5	0.86	0.61	0.05	0.01	1.53	2.03	77	1.4
CV		2.36	37.25	11.76	48.25	35.76	70	2.33	3.23	16.67	1	39.22	18.72	14.64	6.23
Midslope (pedon II)															
Ap	0-17	5.6	0.81	0.09	9	15.83	0.35	0.76	0.56	0.05	0.01	1.38	1.73	80	1.36
AB	17-39	5.7	0.64	0.1	6.4	28.5	0.4	0.77	0.57	0.04	0.01	1.39	1.79	78	1.25
Bt1	39-74	5.25	0.57	0.13	4.38	21	1.2	0.79	0.58	0.05	0.01	1.43	2.63	54.4	1.36
Bt2g	74-135	5.3	0.71	0.13	5.46	18	1.6	0.79	0.58	0.04	0.01	1.42	3.02	63	1.36
Mean		5.46	0.68	0.11	6.31	18.25	0.89	0.78	0.57	0.05	0.01	1.41	2.29	77	1.36
CV		4.03	14.71	18.18	31.22	26.7	68.54	2.56	1.75	20	0	2.13	27.95	24.66	5.21
Crest (pedon I)															
Ap	0-22	5.45	0.81	0.1	8.1	12.31	0.3	0.82	0.61	0.07	0.02	1.52	1.82	84	1.34
AB	25-47	5.7	0.73	0.1	7.3	16.61	0.2	0.82	0.61	0.05	0.01	1.49	1.69	88	1.34
Bt1	47-76	5.65	0.71	0.12	5.92	7.74	0.5	0.82	0.64	0.05	0.01	1.52	2.02	75.25	1.28
Bt2g	76-92	5.75	0.63	0.12	5.25	13.72	0.65	0.82	0.64	0.05	0.01	1.52	2.17	70	1.28
Mean		5.64	0.73	0.11	6.64	12.6	0.41	0.82	0.63	0.06	0.01	1.51	1.93	79	1.31
CV		2.3	9.72	9.09	19.43	22.6	48.78	0	3.17	166.67	1	1.32	10.88	10.27	2.21
LSD(5%)		0.03	0.02	0	4.55	35.58	0.19	0	0	0	0	0.01	0.2	171.07	0

TN= Total nitrogen, C/N= carbon nitrogen ratio, Av, available phosphorous, TE total exch. Basea, ECEC= effective cation exch. Capacity, BS= base saturation

Correlation Matrix

The correlation matrixes are presented in table 5. There was a negative but highly significant correlation between sand and clay (-0.85**) while %BS and ECEC was also negative but highly significant correlation (-0.97**). The positive and highly significant correlations are the silt and clay, clay and ECEC, TN and OC.

Table 5. Correlation matrix of selected physical and chemical Properties of the soils along the Toposequence of Aya River

	Sand	Silt	Clay	SCR	pH	OC	TN	AvP	TEB	ECEC	BS
Sand	1										
Silt	-0.48	1									
Clay	-0.85**	-0.05	1								
SCR	-0.22	0.92**	-0.29	1							
pH(water)	-0.35	-0.13	-0.32	-0.25	1						
Oc	0.08	-0.28	0.08	-0.14	-0.06	1					
TN	-0.14	0.56	-0.18	0.56	-0.27	-0.8**	1				
AvP	0.19	-0.44	0.05	-0.42	0.01	-0.31	0.03	1			
TEB	-0.09	0.58*	-0.24	0.49	0.14	-0.51	0.67*	-0.42	1		
ECEC	-0.88**	0.31	0.81**	0.13	-0.65*	-0.23	0.33	-0.02	0.01	1	
BS	0.86**	-0.26	-0.82**	-0.09	0.64*	0.13	-0.19	-0.04	0.19	-0.97**	1

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level, ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01

Soil Classification

The soils of the study area were classified using USDA Soil Taxonomy system (2015), and correlated with World Reference Base (2006). In classifying these soils, the criteria considered were nature of the epipedon, the types of diagnostic master horizon, the clay content, the organic matter content, the percentage base saturation, the presence, or absence of concretions (plinthitic features), the soil moisture, temperature regimes, diagnostic horizons and soils colour. The soils tends to have more bright hues (reddish brown) due to good aeration, these pedons was classified as in the order as Alfisols because of the presence of Bt horizon, high percentage base saturation and the absence of lamellae, suborder as utsalfs owing to the Ustic moisture regime, great group as Argillic typic ustalfs as the most subsoil horizons were argillic along with high OC contents as well as the high %BS while the preponderance of sand showed psammentic (USDA) correlates to Arenic (WRB). The subgroup was classified Eutric arenic Haplustalfs. The family was classified coarse sandy clay loam, Isohyperthermic, ustalfs and classified as Ogoja sandy clay loam series. This corresponds to Arenic Luvisols (pedons 1 and 2) with fluvic characteristics in pedon 3 (WRB, 2006).

Conclusion

Basaltic soils are rich in intermediate plagioclase feldspar which means they have reserve of weatherable minerals. The physical and chemical limitations of tropical Alfisols can be ameliorated by applying both conservational and good tillage practices. The soil texture was dominated by sand (85.78 %) followed by clay (17.15%), define texture as loamy sand. Soil reaction ranges from strongly acidic in the topsoil to moderately acidic in the

subsoil. The soil pH differ among the different pedons on the toposequence with mean values of 5.50 (Pedon I), 5.46 (Pedon II) and 5.64 (Pedon III). The soils had low BS (%). The total N was also low in concentrations. Available P was in medium concentrations and exch. K^+ and the Na^+ was assessed as very low concentrations and do not pose a threat to soil salinization. Most prominent problems to these soils are high temperature and precipitation. The soil quality and fertility indicators are generally low for these soils; hence soil conservation and use of integrated soil fertility management- organic sources (compost manure), liming, inorganic sources (NPK fertilizers) and crop rotation as well as conservational tillage is recommended. The soils were classified as moderately suitable with limitations in pH and low soil organic matter content.

Reference

- Adisa, K.F., Ojetade J.O., Muda S.A. and Amusan A.A. (2016). Characterization and fertility capability classification of the soils of Shasha River Floodplain, Osun state, Nigeria. *Ife Journal of Agriculture*. Vol 28 (1), 20-34.
- Akamigbo, F.O.R and Asadu C.L.A (1986). The Influence of Topography on Some Soils Parameters in Selected Areas of Anambra State Nigeria. *Nigeria Journal of Soil Sci.* 65: 35-46.
- Asadu, C.L.A. (1990). Soil Resources Management. A Critical Factor in National Development in Challenges of Agriculture, 142-153.
- Atofarati, S.O., Ewulo B.S. and Ojeniyi S.O. (2012). Characterization and Classification of Soils on Two Toposequences at Ile-Olu, Ondo State, Nigeria. *Int. J. of Agric.* Vol.2 (7), 624-650.
- Brady, N. C. and Weil R. R. (1999). The Nature and Properties of Soils, (12th Edition). Published by Prentice Hall' Upper Saddle River, New Jersey. 42 pp.
- Brady, N. C. and Weil R. R., (2014). The Nature and Properties of Soil. Prentice Hall, New Jersey, USA. 12th Edition. 881 pp.
- Chude, V.O., Malgwi W.B., Amapu W.B and Ano O.A. (2011). Manual on Soil Fertility Assessment. Federal Fertilizer Department in Collaboration with National Programme for Food Security, Abuja, Nigeria.
- Daniel, P.R, Alvin Smucker J.M. and Santo D. (2000). Alfafa Root and Shoot Mulching Effect on Soil Hydraulic Properties and Aggregation. *Soil Science Society of America Journal* 64, 725-731.
- Eshett, E.T. (1987). The Basaltic Soil of South Eastern Nigeria: Properties, Classification and Constraints to Productivity. *Journal of Soil Science*. 38, 565 – 571.
- Esu, I.E., Uko U. and Aki E.E. (2015). Morphological, Physicochemical and Mineralogical Properties of Soil Developed From Basalt at Ikom, Cross River State, Nigeria. *NJSS* Vol. 25, 168-180.
- FAO. (2006). World reference base for soil resources by ISSS-ISRIC-FAO. World Soil Resources Report No. 103, Food and Agricultural Organization, Rome, Italy.
- Fisher, R.F and Binkley, D. (2000). Ecology and Management of Forest Soils 3rd Ed. John Wiley and Sons Inc. New York. 201 pp.
- FMANR {Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Natural Resources}(1990). Literature Review on Soil Fertility Investigations in Nigeria, Bobma Publishers, Ibadan 281 pp

Foth, H.D (1990). Fundamentals of Soil Science. 8th Ed. John Wiley and Sons, New York.

Gee, G.W., and Or D. (2002). Particle size analysis in: Dane, J.H., Topp. G.C., (eds). Methods of soil analysis (part 4), Physical methods. Am book series. No. 5 ASA and SSSA Madison, vol. 1., 255-295.

Grossman, R. B. and Reinsch T. G. (2002). Bulk density and linear extensibility in Dane J. H. and Topp G. C. (eds). Methods of soil analysis part 4 Physical Methods. Soil science Soc. Amer. Book Series No. 5 ASA and SSSA, Madison WI, 201 – 228.

Haby, V.A., Russelle M.P. and Skogley E.O. (1990). Testing soils for potassium, calcium and magnesium. In R.L. Westerman (ed.) Soil testing and plant Analysis. 3rd Ed. SSSA, Madison, WI. 181 – 1227.

Hendershot, W.H., Lalande H. and Dequette M. (1993). Soil Reaction and exchangeable Acidity. In: Carter, M.R (ed) Soil sampling and methods of Analysis Canadian soc. of sci, Lawis Pub, London, 141-145.

Imadojemu, P.E., Osujieke D.N., and Obasi S.N. (2017). Evaluation of Fadama Soils Along a Toposequence Proximal to River Donga in Wukari Area of North-East Nigeria. International Journal of Agric. and Rural Dev., SAAT FUTO, Vol. 20(2): 3150-3158.

Juo, A. S. R. and Moorman F.R. (1980). Characteristics of the Toposequences in Southeastern Nigeria and Their Reaction to Potential Agricultural Landuse. *Nigerian Journal of Soil Science* Vol. 1, 46-61.

Kolay, A.K. (2002). Basic concepts of soil science. New age international concept publishers.

Landon, J.R. (1991). Booker Tropical Soil Manual: A Handbook for Soil Survey and Agricultural Land Evaluation in the Tropics and Subtropics, Longman Scientific and Technical, Essex, New York. 474 pp.

Noshadi, E., Hossein A. and Alavipanah S. (2013). Prediction of Surface Soil Colour Using Physicochemical Characteristics and Classification of Vertisol Developed on Deltaic Plain, Turkey. *Open Journal of Soil Science*. 2, 20-27.

Nsor, M. E. and Akamigbo, F. O. R. (2015). Characterization and Land Suitability Evaluation of Soils Derived From Diverse Parent Materials in Central Cross River State Nigeria For Arable Cropping. *Nigerian Journal of Soil Science* Vol. 25, 155-167

Nuga, B.O., Eluwa, N.C., Akinbola, G.E and Wokocho, C.C. (2006). Characterization and Classification of Soils Along a Toposequence in Ikwuano Local Government of Abia State Nigeria. *Agricultural Journal*, 1, 192-197.

Ofem, K. I. and Esu, I. E. (2015). Pedological study of soils Developed on Schist in Biase Biase Local Government Area of Cross River State Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Soil Science*, Vol. 15, 181-193.

Ojo-Atere, J. O., Ogunwale J. A. and Oluwatosin G. A. (2011). Fundamentals of Tropical Soil Science. Evans Brother Limited. Ibadan. 40-47.

Okolo, C.C., Akamigbo F.O.R., Ezeaku P.I., Nwite J.C., Ezeudo V.C., En, J., Ukaegbu E.P., Udegbumam O.N. and Eze N.C. (2011). Impact of Open Cast Mine Land Use on Soil Physical Properties in Enyigba, Southeastern Nigeria and the Implication for Sustainable Land Use Management. *Nigerian Journal of Soil Science*, Vol. 25, 95 - 101.

Oleghe, E. E. and Chokor, J. U. (2014). Effects of gully erosion on soil properties in some soils of Edo state Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Soil Science*. 24(1), 174 – 182.

Osodeke, V. E. (2017). Greedy Tropical Soil: Appeasing the Hungry Soils for Sustainable Food Production. An Inaugural Lecture of the Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike. 14 pp.

Paul, E.A. and Clark F.E. (1989). Soil Microbiology and Biochemistry. Academic Press Inc., San Diego, CA, USA, 273 pp.

Sanchez, P.A. (2019). Properties and Management of Soils in the Tropics. 2nd Edition. Cambridge University Press New York.

Sobieraj, J.A., Elsenber H., Coelho H.R. and Newton B. (2002). Spatial Variability of Soil Hydraulic Conductivity Along a Tropical Rainforest Catena. *Geoderma* 108, 79- 90.

Udo, E.J., Ibia T.O., Ogunwale J.A., Ano A.O. and Esu I.E. (2009). Manual of soils plant and water analyses. Sibon books limited. Lagos. 183pp.

USDA, (2015). Illustrated Guide to Soil Taxonomy version 2.0 September, 2015. 4-10 – 4-60.

Wakene, N. (2003). Assessment of Important Physicochemical Properties of Dystric Udalf (Dystric Nitosols) Under different Management Systems in Bako Area, Western Ethiopia. MSc Thesis, Alemaya University, Alemaya Ethiopia, 93 pp.